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TECHNOLOGY****THE PLIGHT of TECHNOLOGY and LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION TEACHERS in
SELECTED SCHOOLS in the MUNICIPALITY of NAVAL, BILIRAN, PHILIPPINES****Delsa A. Ariaso*, Noel Pricilda Tancinco**

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ABSTRACT

The study generally aimed to ascertain the plight of the Technology Livelihood Education Teachers in the secondary schools in the Municipality of Naval, Biliran. Employing the qualitative research design, 22 teachers were involved in a preliminary survey and all of them were tapped for the in-depth interview. Most of the teachers who were hired underwent the process of applying as arranged by the Division of Biliran with the guidelines mandated by the Department of Elementary Education (DepEd); selection was based on the merit of documents submitted. All of the TLE teachers were hired by personally applying for their positions, without the intervention of any other person, and selection was based on their personal qualifications. Most of the TLE teachers were assigned based on localization and their specialization or major, with a few assigned to fill in the need of a teacher per recommendations of their supervisors. The teaching environment of the schools was generally advantageous and conducive to learning -- classrooms properly constructed, well-ventilated, well-lighted, and functional, except for a few. The school buildings were built on standards which provided safety and protection for the students; although some areas needed minor repairs, repainting and renovation. The TLE teachers were generally satisfied by the support of their school administrators, except for a few who found disappointments with the attitude and behavior of their superior; but they were not satisfied with community support due to the unresponsiveness and lack of cooperation of parents of the students to the needs of their class activities as some parents compelled their children to work at home and earn a living. The overall teaching performance of the TLE teachers was very satisfactory as 77.3 percent of them received above average ratings and none with below average rating. The problems met by the TLE teachers were in line with school facilities and equipment, lack of instructional materials, extra-curricular activities, students' misbehavior, insufficient support from the administration, negative attitudes of school administrators, and insufficient support from the community, instructional materials, and dealing with students. To deal with their problems, they took on a positive approach, a factor which provided them the necessary strength to move on with their teaching job. With their positive outlook, they developed effective strategies to face their predicaments, particularly in terms of personal initiative and resourcefulness. For the improvement of TLE instruction in the secondary schools of Naval, Biliran, major interventions recommended include activation of the utilization of multimedia instructional materials, procurement of adequate equipment and facilities, upgrading of the technical and managerial skills of the TLE teachers, implementation of the Modular Approach to teaching, institutional linkage with funding institutions and agencies. Minor interventions suggested include upgrading of the TLE teachers' qualification through graduate studies, their involvement in the conduct of research, their availability for consultation and upliftment activities with the students, and strengthening of the bond between and among teachers and parents and community.

KEYWORDS: Education Teachers; Livelihood; Plight of Technology and Livelihood Education.**INTRODUCTION**

The plight of TLE teachers is the nature and nurture of their past experiences. It is also conditioned by the type and quality of their experiences in their professional life. Teachers play a dominant role in the education of children. Much has been said of the professional training of teachers, their virtues and dedication to the highest ideals of public service. However, the phase of the teacher's life particularly those teaching Technology Livelihood Education (TLE), which is an often ignored and taken-for-granted subject by many-a-student today without realizing the significant

contribution of TLE subject to their life, has never been properly recognized. The need to look back and discern on the plight of our teachers in the field is an existing scenario which needs to be addressed.

Garcia (2006), in his article on first class teachers stressed that is expected from the TLE teachers -- the burden of the big task of educating students placed on their shoulders. They are mandated to develop their students' potentials to the fullest, for them to live productive lives.

Moreover, EDCOM (ret 2012,) reiterated the challenge to teachers of bringing out the best in their TLE students -- which is a very urgent call since "the quality of Philippine education is continuously declining." It can be noted that TLE subjects are not yet given so much importance by many. To date only a few students take vocational courses, apparently those who do realize that these will lead them to opportunities for employment even if they do not get a college education. In the long run, TLE-takers will realize that technical courses are opportunities for them to uplift their economic capabilities and thus improve their family's standard of living. TLE teachers should themselves also be convinced that TLE subjects are the practical and effective answers to the needs of an impoverished society like ours, and that teaching TLE subjects is essential in equipping our youth with knowledge, skills, and proper attitudes towards work and thus ensure the development and wise utilization of our country's resources. Actually, TLE is the answer to improve peoples' quality of life. Because of the fact that teaching TLE subjects or the basic technologies is essential in equipping the youth with knowledge and skills in order to develop positive rational attitudes towards work and insure the development and wise utilization of the country's resources.

It is on this premise that this study was conceived, considering the fact that in the past there has been no study conducted yet focusing on this aspect.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to ascertain the plight of Technology Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers in selected secondary schools in the municipality of Naval, Biliran. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. Find out the experiences of the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers in the secondary schools in the municipality of Naval, Biliran, in terms of: mode of hiring; mode of teaching assignment; teaching environment; administrative support; and community support.
2. Determine the level of performance of the teachers teaching Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE);
3. Determine the problems met and the coping mechanisms employed by the teachers teaching Technology and Livelihood Education; and
4. Design an intervention scheme for the improvement of the teaching performance of the teachers teaching Technology and Livelihood Education.

FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

Grounded theory is a research method which operates almost in a reverse fashion from traditional social science research. Rather than beginning with a hypothesis, the first step is data collection, through a variety of methods. From the data collected, the key points are marked with a series of codes, which are extracted from the text. The codes are grouped into similar concepts in order to make them more workable. This study was conducted to ascertain the plight of TLE teachers in selected secondary schools in the municipality of Naval, Biliran. The variables involved in the study include the specific experiences of the TLE teachers in terms of mode of hiring, mode of teaching assignment, teaching environment, administrative support, and community support. Problems met and the corresponding coping mechanisms employed by the teachers were gathered and analyzed. The study utilized the descriptive survey design. In conducting the research, a researcher-made questionnaire was given to each respondent. Strengths and weaknesses were identified and a scheme of interventions was formulated to provide ways and means in improving the performance of the teachers.

The illustration of the conceptual framework is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study sought to determine the plight of TLE teachers. It covers only the teachers in the five secondary schools in the municipality of Naval, Biliran. The respondents and subjects of the study were all the 22 secondary TLE teachers in the said secondary schools. Research activity in this regard covered the period from January 2012 to March 2012.

Review of Literature

This portion presents the review of literature and related studies that have bearing in this study.

Technology Livelihood Education. Technology Livelihood Education (TLE) is a set of subjects incorporated in the new secondary school curriculum. It is synonymous with Home Economics (THE) which provides learners in the urban, rural, and sub-urban areas with opportunities to apply basic concepts and principles and relate pertinent values to the home and the world of work.

TLE subjects include four major components: Home Economics, Agricultural and Fishery Arts, Industrial Arts and Entrepreneurship, organized as four units.

Sarmiento (1999), citing the SEDP principles, enunciated that home economics covers home and family living, housing and family economics, foods and applied nutrition and basic clothing. Practical work experience includes managing and caring for the sick, preparing and processing of food, simple sewing and other allied activities. The first two year levels of the subjects are exploratory with 1.5 unit credits and are programmed on a 60-minutes daily frame. In the third and fourth year levels, the subjects are offered as a specialized and intensive course with 2 unit credits and an 80-minutes daily program. The content and practicum of the course through the four-year period may vary from school to school depending on the needs of the learners and the community resources.

The second TLE component comprises plant production, animal production, and fish production. The third component, industrial arts, includes drafting, importance of handicraft and woodworking. Entrepreneurship, the last

component of TLE, deals with concept of entrepreneurship, planning a simple entrepreneurship activity, retailing as entrepreneurial tool, and introduction to computer education.

He further stated that the discipline of home economics encourages a healthy combination of education for vocation and education for a balanced human existence. Home economics as an applied science brings together knowledge from many different disciplines. It provides general knowledge as well as concepts and other fields and application to help individual and families improve their lives. The concern of home economics for the quality of family life continues, but families have changed in large part due to rapid social and technological development. Conditions in society that affect individuals and families, developments in education that affect all subject areas, and advances in knowledge influence the direction and planning of secondary programs.

METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research design was used in this study. This design was found appropriate to the study because it was anchored on the grounded theory which processes concepts and information in an inductive manner. Thus, a survey and narration products of interviews of respondents were the main sources of data. The five secondary schools in the municipality of Naval, Biliran, were the venue of the study. These include Naval State University Laboratory High School, Cathedral School of La Naval, Naval School of Fisheries, Larrazabal National High School, and Lucsoon National High School. The TLE teachers in the five secondary schools comprised the respondents and at the same time the subjects of the study. Twenty-two (22) in number, this was 100 percent of the total number of TLE teachers in the municipality of Naval. A semi-structured questionnaire was utilized during interview. The questionnaire elicits information regarding the profile of the TLE teachers, their experiences in teaching, their level of teaching performance, the problems they encountered in teaching and their coping mechanisms. Observations were also done to validate data and information gathered, capturing significant concerns with the use of a camera. Statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of data on the profile of the TLE teachers and their level of performance. Data on the experience of TLE teachers were treated using the frequency and the percentage while data on the level of performance were treated using the percentage and the weighted mean.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results and discussion of the interview conducted with 22 TLE teachers of the five secondary schools in the municipality of Naval, Biliran are presented based on the objectives of the study.

Experiences of the TLE Teachers

To delve into the experiences of TLE teachers in teaching TLE subjects, 22 teachers from the five secondary schools in the municipality of Naval, Biliran, were interviewed. Observations of their respective areas of work were also done. Topics discussed revolved first around their impressions and feelings of their institutional status, including mode of hiring, mode of teaching assignment, teaching environment, administrative support and community support. Gathered data in this respect are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Experiences of TLE Teachers

<i>Experience</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
1. Mode of hiring		
Through application with interview	16	72.7
Recommended by a politicians		
Hired by the school/university	0	0.0
Volunteered/before hiring		
Total	5	22.7
	1	4.
	22	100.0
2. Mode of teaching assignment		
Based on specialization	17	77.3

Not based on specialization	5	22.7
Total	22	100.0
3. Teaching environment		
Classrooms and laboratories are conducive to learning (infrastructure functional, teaching facilities available, and teachers avail of in-service trainings)	15	68.2
Classrooms and laboratories are not conducive to Learning (infrastructure not functional, lack of teaching facilities, and no in-service trainings for teachers)	7	31.8
Total	22	100.0
4. Administrative support		
Administrator gives support	20	90.9
Administrator does not give any support	2	9.1
Total	22	100.0
5. Community support		
Community is very supportive of school activities and projects	14	63.6
Community does not support any school activity or project	8	36.4
Total	22	100.0

Mode of hiring. Most of the teachers who were hired had undergone the process of applying as arranged by the Division of Biliran with the guidelines mandated by the Department of Elementary Education (DepEd). As revealed in the interviews, prior to hiring, the teacher-applicant had to submit all the authenticated documents to the district heads and the school selection committee. The selection committee arranged the specific schedule of submission of said documents and of the interview. After the interview, the teacher-applicant had to come back for a teaching demonstration; this was a major screening requirement. The entire process in selecting a teacher-applicant was based on the merit of the documents submitted. All of the respondents claimed that they were hired by personally applying for their positions:

Respondent 1: “I have applied for the position with my qualifications without any recommendations from any politician or supervisor.”

Respondent 6: “I was hired as a Social Studies teacher last 2002. Only after four years of being in the service, and perhaps because my high school major subject in TLE was Fish Culture, I was told by my Department Head to teach Fish Culture for lack of teachers and for the influx of students taking Fish Culture as their major subject.”

Respondent 7: “Yes, I applied for the position without any recommendation by a supervisor or politician.”

Respondent 22: “I underwent the ranking process and was fortunate enough to pass, and I was given the item or position of a TLE teacher.”

Based on the responses of the interviewees, it can be gleaned that the mode of hiring of the teachers was based on the official procedures and guidelines set by the DepEd, and that no political intervention was present in the system. This would imply that the practices of the said secondary schools in the mode of hiring of teachers were fair, sound, and just.

Mode of teaching assignment. Most of the TLE teachers were assigned based on the Localization Law. On the other hand, a few teachers shared that their teaching assignments were due to lack of teaching personnel, as decided through recommendations from their supervisors.

Seventeen (17) of the respondents said that their assignments were based on their specialization while the rest of them claimed that their assignments were not based on their specializations. Here are some of the TLE teachers' comments:

Respondent 2: "Yes, my specialization is Fishery, and I am teaching Fishery subjects at the moment."

Respondent 4: "Yes, I think I was assigned based on my specialization which is Fish Culture and Agriculture, and I am teaching the subjects."

Respondent 10: "Yes, I am specialized in Garments Technology, and I am assigned as a TLE teacher teaching Garments Technology."

Respondent 12: "Yes, of course, the present teaching assignments call for majors or specializations, and I am specialized in TLE."

Respondent 14: "Yes, being a BSED graduate, major in TLE, my teaching assignment is very much in line with my specialization."

Based on the information from the respondents, it can be noted that the mode of teaching assignment of the teachers is generally based on their specializations or majors with the exception of a few. This would imply that the teachers could carry out their tasks and assignments well since they taught subjects in line with their fields of specialization.

Teaching environment. This includes the infrastructure, availability of teaching facilities, and in-service trainings. Most of the teachers shared their positive feedback on the environment that they had. They were happy and excited to tell that they were in a place conducive to learning. The classrooms, for instance, were well-ventilated, well-lighted and properly constructed. Only a few mentioned that their rooms were only partly conducive, good or functional. Some of the respondents also stressed that the school buildings were built on standards which provided safety and protection for the students. On the other hand, a few of them had different reactions. They noted that some of their classrooms needed minor repairs, repainting, and renovation of the kitchens for their laboratory works. As far as teaching facilities is concerned, the teachers stressed that absence or lack of instructional materials was the number one problem which they encountered. In fact, TLE textbooks were the main problem to them since almost all of the books were obsolete and were very limited in number. Even at home, no TLE reading materials were available. Teachers had to spend their own money to produce some reading materials because of lack of school funds for that purpose. However, other supplies like manila papers, pentel pens, bond papers, ball pens, chalks, and other supplies needed in teaching were supplied or reimbursed from MOOE. But prior to the provision of MOOE, they bought all their teaching materials with their personal money without any reimbursement made.

When asked about the conditions of their teaching environment, the TLE teachers had these to say:

Respondent 1: "My classroom is conducive to learning. There is no problem with regard to my working relations with my co-teachers."

Respondent 6: "As far as I am concerned, the teaching environment is conducive to learning, and my co-teachers are very much supportive. Exchange of ideas is evidently excellent, especially with my Department Head."

Respondent 9: "In my lecture class, there is no problem; but in my laboratory class, there is, since there are no adequate facilities. Somehow, we teachers make it a healthy environment since we work well among ourselves."

Respondent 14: "Yes, classroom also matters. Students must be comfortable. In my four years of teaching, my relationship with my co-workers has been good. I have not encountered problems with them yet. It is only a matter of patience and understanding."

Respondent 19: "So far, I have good and harmonious relationship with my co-teachers and I am glad and happy that these people surround one another and are supportive and always ready to help me whenever I need them. And I

believe that a good relationship to people as co-workers could help you to become a very successful and effective teacher.”

Findings from the interviews suggest that the teaching environment is advantageous to the TLE teachers.

Administrative support. The TLE teachers in the open claimed that their administrators were very supportive and that they showed their teachers “good attitudes and good treatment.”

One TLE teacher shared that the principal of his school checked her performance through classroom observation four times a week. She was observed when she taught her pupils. Her lesson plans were also checked. She felt very much at ease or comfortable with the administrator. According to her she was very approachable, “with empathy not prejudice,” and always being considerate with the opinion of others. “Our school head involves us in making decisions; she presented her plans to us and always looked after the benefits of the school. She always provides us with financial assistance, and she is respectful to his subordinates. When she corrects, she calls the teacher for a conference; she practices confrontation with the offender alone, not in public. She even always encourages us to take masteral courses in other big universities for our professional growth and to improve our teaching competence.” Most of the TLE teachers had positive feedbacks when it came to internal administrative support. Most of them shared that the administration was responsive to the demands and changing conditions.

However, even if the majority of the teacher stated that they did receive internal administrative support, as to level of their satisfaction, most of them expressed that they were only “partially satisfied.” They noted that the support intended were sometimes hindered by conflicts and issues. Availability of funds and resources were also a hindrance. While several TLE teachers said that they were “very satisfied” with the kind of administrative support they received. More than that, others stressed that they were “not really satisfied.” The latter claimed that they “haven’t been valued, appreciated, nor given much attention by their administrators and those persons of authority.” They just used their “initiative and resourcefulness as well as patience to solve conflicts whenever they arose.”

Listen to specific instances aired out by the TLE teachers outside of formal interview:

One teacher talked about the frustrating experiences of her life as a TLE teacher when she asked financial assistance for Gasul or Gas Range and other equipment needed for the laboratory. She said she was “scolded and insulted in front of the crowd.” It was “really an embarrassing and disgusting moment in my life, with the length of service I have served as a teacher in the school.” She was dismayed because her superior “was judgmental on me, and he did not have the trust and confidence in me, and he could not keep top secrets, and did not even observe the strict sense of confidentiality.”

Another teacher also gave us her feedback on her administrator. She said he was not lazy; he was very active. But the problem was his tantrums; “he cannot hold his temper which sometimes discourages the teacher from respecting him; and we cannot deny the fact that he just cannot be trusted. He involves himself in gossip; this discourages us from respecting him.”

Most of the TLE teachers shared frustrating experiences “when they encounter slow learners in class, when students get zero during quiz, when they are notoriously absent, when they do not follow recipes correctly during cooking, or when they not follow the order in washing dishes.”

Other frustrations, which are more serious, were “when professional jealousy occur; when they are assigned overtime work, but are underpaid; when they encounter hardship in teaching and cope it alone; and lack of textbooks.

A female teacher revealed that she was particularly stressed by the high expectations of her superior when in fact she was only receiving low salary. Like when she was assigned to manage a demonstration pond project of the school, she had to tackle it for good performance despite lack of facilities and minimal financial support from the administration.

Problems were identified here and there -- from the cumbersome and challenging process of ranking after having a license to the pressures in the working environment; in dealing with students, administrators, and stakeholders and community. "As a TLE teacher," according to them, "you must be firm and composed."

There was a teacher who expressed that he had a tactless superior, but he just remained calm and optimistic. He strove hard. "Not all the time people are in good mood," he reasoned. "I just try to understand my superior."

Most memorable experiences of TLE teachers were when "they can share their knowledge and skills in-line with their field of specialization."

They recall memorable joyful moments of their teaching career "when I rendered my first day of teaching as a private school teacher way back in 1993"; "when my students work in the pond during their practicum"; "when my students relate to me what they learned from my teaching"; "when my students successfully accomplish their assigned garments projects"; "when my students properly demonstrate knowledge or transfer techno-demonstration to others"; "when my students perform laboratory work by themselves"; "when my students are industrious and can prepare delicious foods and handle proper table setting"; "when my students passed the NC II qualification test from TESDA"; and "when, because of my students' accomplishments, I achieved the targets of my teaching job."

Community support. As regards community support, the TLE teachers noted that this contributed much for the improvement of their school. The teachers were happy that there was sufficient community support to the school. In fact one teacher shared that he received a support from Mr. Michael Kent Smay; Mr. Smay donated an Optoma Projector for the utilization teaching TLE subject, which was badly needed during discussions to break the monotony of the traditional lecture method.

Some schools received support from majority of the parents of their students. These parents claimed that they were very much supportive of their children through financial assistance for the schools' laboratory. While a few parents neglect being supportive to the school, a good number of them religiously attended activities in the school, such as, PTCA meetings, Christmas Party, *Brigada Eskwela*, and other curriculum-related activities. When it comes to *pentakasi* or *bayanihan*, the parents were "very active, participative and supportive." Some parents were even so supportive as to allow their home equipment and utensils to be brought by their children to school for laboratory purposes. Some TLE teachers claimed that they received personal support from their family and friends. Moral and spiritual support were also afforded them while in some instance financial or material support were received to ease their teaching difficulties.

Were the TLE teachers satisfied with the support they received from their community? Most of them said that they were just "partly satisfied." This was due, they said, to the unresponsiveness and lack of cooperation of some parents of the students to the needs of their class activities, and simply because "there was only minimal support from the community."

Only a few TLE teachers expressed that they were "much satisfied" with the support from the community. With regards to support from parents, they disliked the fact that some parents compel their children to help them work at home and earn a living.

Here are some statements heard from the TLE teachers regarding community support:

Respondent 5: "Yes, I do receive support from my parents and sometimes from the local government units."

Respondent 7: "Nothing great. But just a simple recognition of me as a qualified teacher in my field of specialization is counted by me as a community support."

Respondent 11: "Yes, I receive support -- from my parents. In general, community support to school activities is satisfactory."

Respondent 12: “In spite of the wide expectations we have in whatever mode of delivering technology-based livelihood education, if necessary, support is ironically lacking in linking the learners to best results projected; however, success is still so far achievable.”

Level of Performance of the TLE Teachers

With permission from respective heads of schools, data on the performance of the TLE teachers were extracted from records. A summary of the data gathered are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. TLE Teachers’ Level of Performance

<i>TLE Teacher</i>	<i>Instructional Competence (70%)</i>	<i>Professional & Personal Characteristics (20%)</i>	<i>Punctuality & Attendance (10%)</i>	<i>Plus Factor</i>	<i>Over-All Rating</i>	<i>Des-cription</i>
1	5.875	1.98	0.8	0.5	9.155	VS
2	4.750	1.96	0.9	0	7.610	VS
3	5.112	1.86	1.0	0.5	8.472	VS
4	5.488	1.88	0.8	0.5	8.668	VS
5	6.050	1.92	0.9	0.5	9.370	VS
6	5.858	1.48	0.7	0.5	8.038	VS
7	5.650	1.54	0.9	0	8.090	VS
8	6.050	1.68	0.8	0	8.530	VS
9	5.488	1.68	0.9	0	8.068	VS
10	5.845	1.88	0.8	0	8.525	VS
11	5.765	1.44	0.7	0	7.905	VS
12	5.616	1.48	1.0	0	8.096	VS
13	5.733	1.72	0.9	0	8.353	VS
14	5.865	1.68	0.9	0	8.445	VS
15	5.965	1.68	0.8	0	8.445	VS
16	4.648	1.68	0.8	0	7.128	S
17	4.720	1.48	0.9	0	7.100	S
18	4.872	1.72	0.8	0	7.392	S
19	4.495	1.64	0.7	0	6.835	S
20	4.886	1.54	0.9	0	7.326	S
21	4.945	2.00	1.0	0.5	8.445	VS
22	4.966	1.98	0.9	0	7.846	VS

Performance was rated in terms of instructional competence (70%), professional and personal characteristics (20%), punctuality and attendance (10%), a total of 100 percent. Measured according to a 10-point weighted system scale, the highest possible points given to each term were as follows: instructional competence: 7 points, professional and personal characteristics: 2 points; and punctuality and attendance: 1 point; totaling a weighted point of 10. An addition of 0.5 point plus factor was allowed to increase the possibility of a teacher earning a perfect score of 10 or outstanding performance. In instructional competence, 14 TLE teachers received ratings of 5 points and above, which range is equivalent to “high” (12 teachers or 54.5%) and “very high” (2 teachers or 9.1%) performance. This is 63.6 percent which is the majority of the teachers. This indicates that the TLE teachers generally had very satisfactory instructional competence. It must be noted that none of the teachers received a rating below 4 points. This finding would imply that these teachers were qualified to handle TLE subjects.

The professional and personal characteristics of the TLE teachers rated within the range of “high” (15 teachers or 50%) and “very high” (5 teachers or 22.7%) as they scored 1.6 points and above. This the great majority (72.7%) of the teachers, which indicates that in terms of professional and personal characteristics, the TLE teachers were well above average. This finding would imply that, again, the teachers were very much qualified to teach TLE subjects. In terms of punctuality and attendance, all of the TLE teachers received ratings of 0.6 points and above. This ranged

from “high” (13 teachers or 59.1%) and “very high” (9 teachers or 40.9%) performance. Since this is 100 percent of the teachers, this connotes that all TLE teachers were very time conscious and thus very good time managers. Implied in this finding could be that these teachers would be efficient and effective TLE teachers. Six (6) or 27.2 percent of the TLE teachers received the plus factor of 0.5. This means that these teachers were seen by their superiors as good leaders in the service. This factor (measured by points not to exceed 2 points) was found by supervisors in terms of the following: rendering assistance to school activities such as helping a co-teacher improve his or her teaching competence; assisting school administrators in planning and managing in-service training; serving as a consultant in the preparation of supplementary instructional materials; serving as a demonstration teacher on innovative teaching techniques; showing efficient classroom management; conducting action research whose findings and recommendations have been adopted by the school or district; and serving as a subject area coordinator or chairman in the district or division. The total weighted points and the percentage of the teachers receiving the plus factor, however, are not significant as to improve the overall picture of the level of performance of the TLE teachers as a whole.

In summary, as shown in Table 1, the overall teaching performance of the TLE teachers was very satisfactory, as indicated by their total ratings which ranged from 7.61 weighted points to 9.37 weighted points. The teachers receiving these ratings comprise the great majority (77.3%). Thus we can safely say that these TLE teachers were efficient and effective teachers in their field.

THE PROBLEMS MET AND THE COPING MECHANISMS

Employed by the TLE Teachers

Throughout the survey, the researcher was very much keen on and eager to determine the primary problems met by the TLE teachers.

Problems met. The study revealed that among these problems met by the respondents were in line with school facilities and equipment, lack of instructional materials, extra-curricular activities, and students’ misbehavior, insufficient support from the administration, support from the community, instructional materials, and dealing with students.

1. *Lack of facilities and equipment.* Most of the TLE teachers shared their frustrations on what they considered their number one problem in teaching TLE subjects. This was the lack of equipment, facilities, and tools both in the classroom and in the laboratory. “Such situation is really an impediment for a better and relevant instruction; these are vital for laboratory exploration and demonstration,” so they said. There were just times, they recalled, that we teachers and students alike could not do the assigned tasks due to this problem.”

2. *Lack of funds.* In addition to the lack of equipment, facilities, and tools, the TLE teachers also complained of lack of funds. This aggravated the first problem. How could we move on with certain laboratory activities and projects which require materials that needed to be bought as they are not supplied by the school. “We had to resort to using our own pocket money or require students to contribute, which funds were themselves minimal. Many parents already complain about such contributions. Even the meaning of Parents-Teachers’ Association (PTA) one time was jokingly converted to ‘*Pastilan, Tatay, Amotan’ na pud!* (Have pity, father, contribution again!).”

2. *Lack of instructional materials.* The third problem was on the unavailability or simple lack of instructional materials. Reading materials such as books, computer softwares or cds, projectors, and the like were just not enough for the number of students using them. The TLE teachers strongly believed that these instructional materials serve as guide and bolster the enthusiasm of the students to study in advance and motivate them to learn more. Computer assisted instruction was indeed a factor that motivated the students to become active participants in the teaching-learning process and thus enhanced their academic performance.

3. *Extra-curricular activities.* School extra-curricular activities also posed as a major problem to the TLE teachers. These activities were seen as “a predicament towards the continuity of class discussion.” Many-a-times classes were dismissed or not held to allow students to participate in school programs or activities not related to their lessons. Especially in times when there are special occasions such as *Linggo ng Wika*, nutrition month, intramurals, proms, and other school or community celebrations, where the students excuse themselves from classes to attend practice or

preparations for the said activities. "If the discussion is at stake, student's learning is at stake as well," thus reason the teachers.

4. *Students' Misbehavior.* As to students, the TLE teachers were in consensus in saying that "they become frustrated when it comes to students' misbehavior, like when they do not pay attention to the discussion or listen to instructions properly." The believed that such behavior is a hindrance to learning and a nuisance to the progress of lesson delivery.

5. *Insufficient support from the school administration.* A few of the TLE teachers aired out their concern on insufficient support from their administration, particularly in terms of providing equipment, facilities, and tools for the students' use. Others complain of school heads' unconcern on settling the issue of lack of instructional materials for their students. There were school administrators who disregarded outright requests of their teachers for the provision of these materials.

6. *Negative attitudes of the school administrators.* This is also seen by a number of TLE teachers as a major problem. One recalled an incident which she considered the worst and saddest experience she had with her principal. For some mistake she committed unintentionally, her attention was called by her superior and was insulted and scolded by her in front of the other teachers and students. Another teacher testified that she was under an administrator who had no patience, and who oftentimes showed undesirable attitude towards her subordinates and even towards her; sometimes she was rude. "She just had no smooth interpersonal relationship with her teachers, which is very much needed in the working environment."

Another teacher also shared her sentiments about the biased treatment her administrator had of her co-teachers. "This administrator did not observe ethical standards based on the Code of Ethics; he even had no sense of respect to his subordinates. He failed to establish trust and confidence with his teachers for the fact that he assigned teachers to serve as his spies on the behavior of his teachers." "Worse was that he always listened to rumors which he very easily spread through gossip." "He failed to respect his teachers and often insulted his subordinates without giving them the opportunity to explain their side.

7. *Insufficient support from the community.* Another major problem encountered by the TLE teachers was the insufficient support from the community. While the schools lacked budget for their TLE programs, students' parents ever presumed that the schools and their programs were funded by the government; thus we do not see any parent or official of the community take the initiative to show concern and see to it that these programs function well and profitably. TLE teachers find themselves "at a loss trying to let both ends meet."

Coping mechanisms. Given the above stated problems encountered by the teacher-respondents as to teaching Livelihood Education, the following were the coping mechanisms employed. For the TLE teachers to cope with their problems in classroom and laboratory activities, a positive approach to dealing with their difficulties was a factor which provided them the necessary strength to move on with their teaching job. Thus no sooner did they realize that they had developed effective strategies to face their predicaments. Coming out of the interviews, one solid strategy was found by them effective: personal initiative and resourcefulness. To lessen the burden and worry due to lack of equipment and facilities and inadequate support from the administration and community, TLE teachers resorted to their own initiative and resourcefulness. This usually came in forms of action such as described by the following statements:

"I just bring my own laboratory tools such as cooking tools and utensils so we can proceed with our laboratory activities."

"I just give take-home activities and assignments in order not to impede the continuity of classes due to extra-curricular activities."

"I improvise learning handouts and materials and give them to my students so they could study them in advance."

"I do personal study and research to produce advanced handouts to my students."

Intervention Scheme

For the improvement of TLE instruction in the secondary schools of Naval, Biliran, interventions obviously need to be done. The TLE teachers themselves aired out the following major recommendations.

Intensify the utilization of multimedia instructional materials. The use of multimedia resources was found to be an effective tool for arousing the interest and enthusiasm of the TLE students in their studies. Moreover this is a technique which has been proven to be effective in the delivery of lessons as they touch the human faculties and senses for learning.

In this respect, the necessary and functional multimedia resources should be provided and made adequate by the school administration.

Procure adequate equipment and facilities. Laboratories are not true and effective laboratories if they do not have the proper equipment, facilities, and tools or utensils for demonstration or experiment activities. There is no question as to the facility and effectiveness of lesson delivery and skill development with the use of these resources.

School administrators should assess the needs of their laboratories and find ways and means to provide those needs.
Upgrade the technical and managerial skills of the TLE teachers. With the fast advancement of information technology, TLE teachers need to keep themselves abreast with the times. New developments in the TLE trade are fast in coming, and if the TLE teachers remain and just feel content with what technical and managerial know-how and skills they possess, they and their students would be lost in the new trends of TLE education.

In that light, school administrators should regularly assess the training needs of their TLE teachers. They should send them to special training in advanced technical and managerial skills. Better still, they should likewise undergo such training to equip themselves properly in handling the specializations they offer and manage in their school.

To support this concern, school administrators should also find ways and means to secure funding for this program, such as linking with funding and research institutions.

Implement the Modular Approach to teaching. From experience, the TLE teachers found the Modular Approach to teaching very convenient and very effective. It is a “light” mode of lesson delivery catered to the students’ level of understanding and comprehension. It emphasizes learner-”focus” where the abilities, capabilities, and attitudes of students are harnessed and put into action. Thus, with it, student learning is maximized.

In line with this, TLE teachers should be provided with the standardized and upgraded modules and, if they are not yet available, the TLE teachers should be made to undergo special and upgraded training in module-making.

School administrators should then assess the competencies of their TLE teachers in the Modular Approach to teaching, send them to specialized training and, if funds are wanting, link with funding agencies in the government and private institutions.

Institutional linkage with funding institutions and agencies. Owing to the shortage of funds in secondary schools, school administrators should establish linkage with funding and research institutions. There are many available both in our country and abroad. It’s a matter of identifying them, contacting them, and establishing rapport with the top managers of these agencies, and requesting them by way of a program or project proposal as an intervention scheme directed to answer the needs of the TLE program of the school.

Other suggestions. The TLE teachers to incorporate into the intervention scheme the upgrading of their qualification through graduate studies, their involvement in the conduct of research, their availability for consultation and upliftment activities with the students, and the strengthening of the bond between and among teachers and parents and community.

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: The TLE teachers undergo the mode of hiring which follows the legal process of ranking designed by the Division Office of Biliran; the hired teachers are all certified and licensed; the mode of assignment follows the Localization Law and is based on accredited specialization of the teacher; the teaching environment is generally conducive to teaching and learning, with some areas needing improvement; support from the school administration and support from the community were minimal and limited and most of the TLE teachers respondents were just not satisfied with them. Also, the overall teaching performance of the TLE teachers was very satisfactory. In instructional competence, majority of the TLE teachers have high ratings; in professional and personal characteristics, the great majority have high ratings also; and in punctuality and attendance, all have high ratings. Only a few of the TLE teachers receive a plus factor of 0.5. The problems met by the TLE teachers include inadequate school facilities and equipment, lack of instructional materials, over-done extra-curricular activities, students' misbehavior, insufficient support from the administration, negative attitudes of school administrators, insufficient support from the community, and difficulties in dealing with students. To deal with their problems, the TLE teachers take on a positive approach, a factor which provides them the necessary strength to move on with their teaching job. With their positive outlook, they develop effective strategies to face their predicaments, particularly in terms of personal initiative and resourcefulness. For the improvement of TLE instruction in the secondary schools of Naval, Biliran, a suggested intervention scheme includes the intensification of the utilization of multimedia instructional materials, procurement of adequate equipment and facilities, upgrading of the technical and managerial skills of the TLE teachers, implementation of the Modular Approach to teaching, institutional linkage with funding institutions and agencies. The scheme also includes minor interventions such as upgrading of the TLE teachers' qualification through graduate studies, their involvement in the conduct of research, their availability for consultation and upliftment activities with the students, and strengthening of the bond between and among teachers and parents and community.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are forwarded: Utilization of multimedia instructional materials should be activated; the necessary and functional multimedia resources should be provided and made adequate by the school administration. Adequate equipment and facilities especially for classrooms and laboratories should be procured. School administrators should assess the needs of their classrooms and laboratories and find ways and means to provide those needs. The technical and managerial skills of the TLE teachers should be regularly upgraded. School administrators should regularly assess the training needs of their TLE teachers and send them to special training in advanced technical and managerial skills. Better still, they should likewise undergo such training to equip themselves properly in handling the specializations they offer and manage in their school. To support this concern, they should also find ways and means to secure funding for this program, such as linking with funding and research institutions. The Modular Approach to teaching should be implemented properly. The TLE teachers should be provided with the standardized and upgraded modules and, if they are not yet available, the TLE teachers should be made to undergo special and upgraded training in module-making. School administrators should then assess the competencies of their TLE teachers in the Modular Approach to teaching, send them to specialized training and, if funds are wanting, link with funding agencies in the government and private institutions. School administrators should establish linkage with funding and research institutions and agencies. The TLE teachers should upgrade their qualification through graduate studies, their involvement in the conduct of research, their availability for consultation and upliftment activities with the students, and the strengthening of the bond between and among teachers and parents and community. Replication studies should be conducted in other schools and universities to document the personal experiences of TLE teachers to obtain a clear and better picture of their plight in their career as harbingers of the good news of Technology and Livelihood Education.

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